

Violence against Women: A Study on Cases Filed and Disengagement

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Abstract:- The prevalence of violence against women is observed in the recent years yet there has been a low rate of prosecution and conviction of perpetrators in because of attrition and disengagement after filing the case taking into consideration that the victim's participation and cooperation are essential in the administration of justice. With these, the study aims to determine the difference in the proportion of cases and understand the reasons for victim disengagement through the use of a quantitative study specifically the triangulation method. Findings suggest that there is a significant difference in the proportion of cases handled by the police and prosecutors level which was computed using the z-test which implies that not all reported cases achieve a successful prosecution. The study also used a t-test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variance wherein the results show that there is no significant difference in the weighted mean of the respondents which denotes that similar reasons are encountered may it be on the police or prosecutors level. Concerning reasons for victim disengagement, the respondents encounters family intervention, reconciliation, child-related reasons and lack of financial support that halts the processing of violence against women cases. To sum it up, the difference in the proportion of cases and the reasons for victim disengagement boils down to the high valuation of the family that often leads to over-reliance on the mediation process resulting in repeated victimization and non pursuing of cases.

Keywords:- Violence, Victimization, Victim disengagement, prosecution, attrition, mediation, reconciliation, intervention, investigation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Evidence of research shows the prevalence of violence against women, where the reported cases of domestic violence represent only a very small part of the problem also known as the “iceberg” of domestic violence (Gracia, E., 2004, July). The United Nations defines violence against women as “any act of gender-based violence that results in or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or mental harm or suffering to women (World Health Organization, 2019, August 11). Added by Pelt, N. V. L. (2000) that spouses are extremely vulnerable to anger from the other spouse. Women are more likely to become victims of Domestic Violence, but once they have experienced it, their chances of becoming repeat victims are much higher compared to men (Walby & Allen, 2004 as cited by Humphreys A., 2019). In a similar study, those who have children in common with the offender and those who obtain a restraining order have a greater risk of victimization and most repeat victims are repeatedly victimized by the same

offender whereby the type of victimization and frequency they suffer vary over time (Mele, M., 2006).

Victims of violence against women cases are affected by many reasons that affect their decision in the filing and non-filing of cases against the abuser which usually results in victim retraction and attrition. Common reasons are the following but not limited to economic dependence, consideration of children, and problems in the criminal justice system response in related cases. It was recognized that during court proceedings victim retraction is almost universally viewed by criminal justice officials as a problematic outcome consequently policy initiatives have been designed to increase support to victims in the hope that more will decide to continue with their cases instead of retracting their statements. Lastly, victims' testimonies are very essential in the legislation of domestic violence cases, but research shows that victims' reason for retraction and attrition is an existing phenomenon that is needed to be understood.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Victim retraction and disengagement is a significant issue in the successful prosecution of Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) cases that creates 'justice gap' which refers to the high proportion of cases reported to the police that drop out at various points in the system also known as attrition (Hester M., 2006 and Sleath, E. and Smith, L. L., 2016). Thus, findings suggest that support contact with the prosecutor's office was associated with reduction in police-reported IPV, regardless of the victim's wish to proceed (Cerulli, C., Kothari, C. L., Dichter, M., Marcus, S., Wiley, J., & Rhodes, K. V., 2014). Furthermore, Robinson A., & Cook D. (2006) claimed that those working to support victims felt that fewer women are likely to retract if they are properly supported and fully informed.

When it comes to police arrest, findings of the study by Falcon, M., & Lopez, A. (2014), explained that police officers cannot intervene when it comes to the removal of the abuser from the home since he had the same right to the residence. Arrest was a likely response when officers were asked to imagine they witnessed a victim's injuries and heard statements about an assault in a case scenario (Saunders, D. G., Prost, S. G., & Oehme, K. 2016). In addition, police officers conduct arrest if it may have indicated a more serious crime and factors to be considered are severity of crime, presence of children, presence of an injunction, and victim injury (Tatum, K. M., & Pence, R., 2015). Further, Stalans, L. J., & Finn, M. A. (2006) posited that there is a comparison between experienced officers and rookie officers in arresting perpetrators in IPV cases. Similarly, only 18% of frontline

officer disagreed that they needed more freedom in deciding how to handle situations at domestic abuse call (Reid L., 2017).

Apart from the factors affecting victim attrition and disengagement, the study of Raj, A., Livramento, K. N., Santana, M. C., Gupta, J., & Silverman, J. G. (2006) in the South Asians in the United States study demonstrate that abuse by in-laws includes emotional abuse, awareness or support of IPV, and direct physical abuse. Additionally, Fuchsel, C. L. M. (2013), identified that factors like experience of childhood sexual abuse, domestic violence, and the role of familism affects victimization. Similarly, Women's Police Station Offices were specifically perceived as spaces where women would initially go to seek legal assistance but these women viewed those working in the criminal justice system as preferring to and actively avoiding involvement in private sphere disputes (Stephens, D., & Eaton, A., 2020). Another identified issue in the escalation of domestic violence is culture. One example is in European countries where initiatives have, however, tended to exist in isolation from strategies on violence against women and girls from majority groups (Dustin, M. 2016).

It is also worth noting the effects of violence against women. Ammar, N. (2012), identified that the trauma from an abusive relationship creates significant distress for the victim that leads women to stay. Violent experiences also lead to low self-esteem, depression, and suicidal ideas in as much as being ambivalent in staying and enduring violence in silence until they cannot tolerate it anymore (Loke, A. Y., Wan, M. L. E., & Hayter, M., 2012). In relation to sexual risk behavior, Woerner, J., & Sullivan, T. P. (2019) study suggest that intimate partner violence victimization is a strong predictor by having multiple close friendships buffered by the effects of social disconnection. A similar study by Artz, L. (2011) identified that out of 251 respondents a total of 469 children who had been, and continued to be, psychologically damaged by the abusive environments they were exposed. Further Iratzoqui, A. (2017) study found that childhood and adolescent domestic victimization were directly and indirectly linked to adult intimate partner victimization.

In the Philippines, World Economic Forum, 2013 as cited by Clamor W. 2018 stated that it ranked as 5th out of 144 countries in terms of gender equality but in contrary, 19% of women have experienced physical or sexual violence, yet only 6% percent report to a formal source (Philippine Statistics Authority - PSA & ICF, 2018 as cited by Garcia, T., 2020). In terms of filing charges, the study of García-Jiménez, M., Cala-Carrillo, M., & Trigo, M. (2019) indicated that only 21.9% of women in this study dropped charges however, disengagement does not mean that women do not try to end the violence actively, but they are using different strategies to achieve it.

In the City of Baguio, there was an alarming increase in the number of violent cases committed against women in the last three years with a recorded 66 cases from January to October, an 11 percent increase from the previous year's

59 cases (See, D. A., 2021, December 3). To add that in the Cordillera region, most reported cases that are settled because of the intervention of influential family members aside from the fact that those being charged are the bread winners of their families, thus, the need for them to free their family member for them to survive (H., 2018, November 20). This is also confirmed by the study of Johnson H., & Fraser J., (2011) and Hopkins, A. (2019) that victims sympathy and concerns on the abuser in terms of their employment especially if she is financially dependent on her partner. In short, gender-based violence is not only recorded among low-income people, although many women in poverty and living in unfavorable backgrounds have less alternatives to escape from violence (Malgesini, G., S. forza, L., & Babovic, M., 2018, July 31). In connection with mediation process of violence against women cases, Humphreys C., & Carter R. (2006) stated that a continued over-reliance on mediation, dispute resolution and diversionary programs inappropriately replaces criminal justice and protective action responses.

A. Statement of the Problem and Hypothesis

This study aimed to identify if there is a significant difference in the proportion of violence against women cases and the reasons of victim disengagement in the police and prosecutors level which entirely affects successful prosecution and probable convictions of perpetrators. In light of this, the study seeks to answer this research question:

Is there a significant difference in the proportion of cases reported in the police level and cases filed in the prosecution level and cases dismissed?

Ho: There is no significant difference in the proportion of cases reported in the police level and cases filed in the prosecution level and cases dismissed.

Is there a significant difference the level of agreement of the respondents in terms of reasons of victims disengagement in violence against women cases as perceived by the police personnel and prosecutor?

Ho: There is no significant difference the level of agreement of the respondents in terms of reasons of victims disengagement in violence against women cases as perceived by the police personnel and prosecutor.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The study used a quantitative design specifically triangulation method. This design is used when a researcher wants to directly compare and contrast quantitative statistical results with qualitative findings or to validate or expand quantitative results with qualitative data. The Triangulation Design is a one-phase design in which researchers implement the quantitative and qualitative methods during the same timeframe and with equal weight (Creswell, D., 2006, May 16). The study focused on the reasons of victim disengagement in the police and prosecutors level.

B. Population and Locale of the Study

The study used total enumeration and the respondents were chosen based on their knowledge and direct experience in dealing with violence against women cases reported and filed from Baguio City Police Office- Women and Children Protection Division (BCPO-WCPD) and Baguio City Justice Hall. The table below indicates the population of the study (See Table 1).

RESPONDENTS	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Police Personnel	52	72%
Public Prosecutors	20	28%
TOTAL	100	

Table 1: Respondents' Profile

C. Research Instrument

The study made use of a questionnaire to gather data from police and prosecutors office concerning number of cases of violence against women in the City of Baguio from 2019-2021. It also includes the reasons of victims disengagement to determine the nature of abuse, current status and reasons that affects the victim in disengaging from the police or prosecutors level. The study also used an unstructured interview guide to corroborate the findings of the study.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher humbly asked permission by preparing a letter addressed to Dr. Cherry Ann A. Cabarrubias, Dean of the College of Criminal Justice Education as endorsed by Dr. Robino D. Cawi, Graduate Program Coordinator. After its approval, the researchers conducted an orientation among the respondents and informed them of the purpose and nature of their participation in the study. In gathering the needed data, the researcher asked permission from the head of the BCPO-WCPD and Baguio City Prosecutors Office to collect the data of cases reported and filed in their respective office. Followed by the letter addressed to the respondents before administration of the questionnaires and conduct of interview which was conducted via online specifically Outlook Form and Zoom meeting. Consequently, the data gathered were subjected to statistical analysis and interpretation with the help of a statistician.

E. Statistical Treatment

In the treatment of data, the questionnaire was subjected to reliability testing using the Spearman Prophecy Brown which is applied to the correlation to determine the reliability. This is often used with dichotomous variables that are scored 0 for incorrect and 1 for correct using the formula below:

$$r_{tt} = \frac{2r_{hh}}{1 + r_{hh}} \quad (d)$$

In the treatment of data based on the case reported, case filed in the police and prosecutors level.

Oneway z-test hypothesis testing are the statistical calculations that can be used to compare population averages to a sample's. A z-test will compare a sample to a defined population that is typically used for dealing with problems relating to large samples (i.e., $n > 30$) (Thakur, M., 2022, May 20). The formula used is stated below:

$$z\text{-statistic} = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu_0}{\sigma/\sqrt{n}}$$

Following the design of the study, frequency count, weighted mean and t-test was used to identify if there a significant difference between the reasons of victim retraction as perceived by the police officers and prosecutors. T-test: Two sample Assuming Unequal Variance to test the null hypothesis. It is a type of inferential statistics to determine whether there is a significant difference between the means of two (2) groups (Siegle, 2015). Where t is the t -value, x_1 and x_2 are the means of the two (2) groups being compared, s^2

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{s^2(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2})}}$$

is the pooled standard error of the two (2) groups, and n_1 and n_2 are the numbers of observations in each of the groups using the formula below:

F. Ethical Consideration

Informed consent was obtained by detailing the purpose of the study and personal information were not sought to ensure the respondents' anonymity. To further protect the respondents, once the data analysis had taken place, the outlook form used in the data gathering were deleted permanently.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the data, analyses, and interpretation of the data gathered in the study.

A. The difference in the proportion of cases reported and filed in the police level

To determine the difference in the proportion of violence against women cases, z-test was used in the data. Table 2 illustrates the data on the cases reported and filed in the police level. The proportion of filed cases equal to 30.20% is lower than the cases being reported which is 69.80%. This decrease is statistically significant as indicated by a p-value of 0.03 which is lower than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). (See Table 2).

Cases	%	z	p
Reported	69.80	11.92	0.03*
Filed	30.20		

Table 2: Cases reported and filed in the police level

This implies that the victims tend to ignore filing the cases they reported at the police level. To add that, women were more likely to have experienced domestic abuse than

men (7.5% compared with 4.3%), which translates to an estimated 1.2 million female victims and 713,000 male victims (ONS, 2017 as cited by Humpreys A., 2019). In relation to this , findings from Association for Progressive Communications (APC). (2013, April 10) explained that in the Philippines ,One in five women aged 15-49 experienced physical violence since age 15. Seventy percent (70%)of physical abuse cases occur in homes whereby fourteen point four percent(14.4%)of married women experience physical violence from their husband.

B. The difference in the proportion of cases filed and reported in the prosecution level

Furthermore, *Table 3* shows the proportion of cases filed and dismissed at the prosecution level. It can be noted that the proportion of cases being filed which is 27.55% is lower than the dismissed cases equal to 72.45%. This decrease is statistically significant as indicated by a p-value of 0.02 which is lower than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). (See *Table 3*).

Cases	%	z	p
Filed	27.55	13.5	0.02*
Dismissed	72.45		

Table 3: Cases filed and reported in the prosecution level

This implies that the victims tend to disengage during the case processing. A similar problem is found out in the study of ONS, 2017 as cited by Humpreys A.,(2019), 54% of unsuccessful prosecutions were due to either victim retraction, victim non-attendance or evidence of the victim not supporting the case resulting to the high percentage of cases that are halted due to victim retraction/non-attendance. This does not only creates a problem in the police level but in the entirety of criminal justice system wherein justice gap is being identified. According to Hester (2006) and Sleath, E. and Smith, L. L. (2016) , Criminal justice agencies have been significantly criticized in relation to IPV cases, in particular in relation to the 'justice gap'.

Meanwhile *Table 4* , shows the weighted mean on the level of agreement by the police personnel on the reasons of victim disengagement. As perceived by the respondents of the study who are the policewomen assigned in the BCPO-WCPD has a general weighted average of 2.90 which means that the respondents agree in the reasons of victims non filing of cases wherein the top two indicators with highest mean is reconciliation and child related reasons. (See *Table 4*).

Reasons as perceived by Police Officers	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Reconciliation	3.31	Strongly Agree
4. Child related reasons	3.29	Strongly Agree
18. No information provided	3.19	Agree
19. intervention of family members	3.19	Agree
17. perfunctory- victim only reported but does not wish to make a statement or support prosecution and attend court	3.17	Agree
8. lack of financial assistance	3.12	Agree
6. did not want to punish partner	3.06	Agree
5. temporary removal of partner in the house	3.04	Agree
14. fear of the offender	2.98	Agree
3. wanting to forget past relationship	2.90	Agree
9. to avoid neighborhood gossip	2.83	Agree
12. uncooperative with law enforcement investigation	2.79	Agree
11. denial of offense	2.77	Agree
2. End of relationship	2.76	Agree
16. mental health issues of the victim	2.75	Agree
13. disengaged with the police level	2.73	Agree
15. substance abuse and misuse related problems of the victim	2.71	Agree
10. do not understand criminal justice process regarding the case	2.65	Agree
20. victims are to be blamed	2.46	Disagree
7. negative view on court proceedings	2.45	Disagree
General Weighted Average	2.90	Agree

Table 4: Level of agreement on the reasons of victim disengagement as perceived by the police officers

In terms of reconciliation, This implies that the police officers encounters a lot of victims that ends up going back in an abusive relationship which in return results to repeated victimization. In relation with the study of

Ammar, N. (2012), it identified that repeated victimization is caused by the trauma from abusive relationship that leads women to stay in an abusive relationship and responds in less adaptive ways. This can be in relation to Learned

Helplessness Theory that explains experiencing repeated beatings or other abuse may lead a woman to become passive because she feels that nothing she does will result in a positive outcome. (Hyde-Nolan M., &Juliao T., 2010).Lastly, in the findings of Balandi C., (2018), found out that various types of abuses such as physical, emotional or psychological , sexual and economic abuses are experiences that haunt the victims of intimate partner violence all through their lives.

Moreover victims especially mothers are being selfless because they always consider first their children but as explained by Davenport, B. (2016), simply being in an abusive environment is a form of emotional abuse for your children.In line with social learning theory that stated children who grow up in violent/ abusive families may learn violent/ abusive behaviors , imitate those behaviors and then repeat those behaviors in their future

relationship(Hyde-Nolan M., &Juliao T., 2010). Backed up by Psy.D., W. M. (2011), that being violent may be a root of a violent household and legacies from osur family of origin that leads to cycle of violence.

To add that statistics shows , among women aged 15-49 who have ever experienced physical or sexual violence and sought help to stop the violence, 45.1% sought help from own family, 28.5% from friends and neighbors, and 14.5% from in-laws. Only 9.3% went to the police and 6.0 % to a social service organization(APC,2013, April 10).

Meanwhile *Table 5* , shows the weighted mean on the level of agreement by the public prosecutor on the reasons of victim disengagement with a general weighted average of 2.96 which means that the respondents agree in the reasons of victims disengagement.(*See Table 5*).

Reasons as perceived by Police Officers	WeightedMean	Interpretation	Rank
19. Intervention of family members	3.40	Strongly Agree	1
2. End of relationship	3.30	Strongly Agree	2
4. Child related reasons	3.30	Strongly Agree	3
8. lack of financial assistance	3.30	Strongly Agree	4
16. mental health issues of the victim	3.25	Strongly Agree	4
5. temporary removal of partner in the house	3.10	Agree	4
3. wanting to forget past relationship	3.05	Agree	7
14. fear of the offender	3.05	Agree	8
17. perfunctory- victim only reported but does not wish to make a statement or support prosecution and attend court	3.05	Agree	8
1. Reconciliation	3.00	Agree	8
9. to avoid neighborhood gossip	2.95	Agree	11
10. do not understand criminal justice process regarding the case	2.95	Agree	12
15. substance abuse and misuse related problems of the victim	2.95	Agree	12
11. denial of offense	2.85	Agree	12
6. did not want to punish partner	2.80	Agree	15
13. disengaged with the police level	2.80	Agree	16
18. No information provided	2.80	Agree	17
12. uncooperative with law enforcement investigation	2.75	Agree	17
20.victims are to be blamed	2.35	Disagree	19
Negative view on court proceedings	2.20	Disagree	20
GWA	2.96	Agree	

Table 5: Level of agreement on the reasons of victim disengagement as perceived by the Public Prosecutors

This implicates that victims have initially engaged in the case processing but later on disengages in the case processing due to the intervention of family members which later on results to attrition of cases. In a related study,a continued over-reliance onmediation, dispute resolution and diversionary programs inappropriately replaces criminaljustice and protective action responses.It is difficult to assess whether anyimprovements in reporting and prosecution have occurredand violence against womenbecomes invisible within the police and judicial system(Humphreys C., & Carter R. , 2006).Römkens, R. (2006)also argued that on the part of the victimcurrent tendencies toward criminalization in domestic violence interventions can have an unintended violent impact for victims who are either excluded from the program or are

forced into a criminal justice regime that might not be in their primary interest.

The role of authority of the familial members were consistently considered as the support system of victims however these support systems firmly believes that it should be settled as a private matter and do not initiate getting help for the victim (Stephens, D., & Eaton, A. , 2020).This is also confirms the claims of family systems theory which is based on the idea that each individual should be viewed not in isolation but in terms of the interactions, transitions, and relationships within the family that influence one another and contribute to the maintenance of particular patterns of behavior(Hyde-Nolan M., &Juliao T., 2010).

To add that there has been mediation from both of the families to note that they are coming from the same province

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>Police Officer</i>	<i>Prosecutor</i>
Mean	2.9075	2.9595
Variance	0.066304	0.09191
Observations	20	20
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	37	
t Stat	-0.58465	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.281166	
t Critical one-tail	1.687094	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.562332	
t Critical two-tail	2.026192	

and ethnicity. She stated that, *“Our family decided not to file a case anymore despite its violation because I want to end totally my relationship with him. His family has also been consistent in visiting me and asking for reconsideration not to file a case especially so that we came from same province and vicinity as they term it “kailyan”.*

Closely linked to the construct of sympathy were externalizing the blame onto alcohol or victims blaming themselves and sympathy to the abuser. This is also related to cognitive dissonance theory whereby it allows her to view the abuser as someone she loves and as a positive factor in her life that will remain in place (Hopkins, A., 2019). Victims also tend to blame external factors that justifies the action of their partner like intoxication wherein 28.8% of women reported experiencing any form of intimate partner violence and 92.9% of women reported their partner being intoxicated at least sometimes. Intoxication was significantly associated with all 3 types of intimate partner violence (Kerridge, B. T., & Tran, P., 2016). In corroboration, Victim “A” stated that, *“During our six years of relationship, I have been very vocal on the abuse my husband is doing to me to my mother-in-law but her response was to always forgive her son and to understand his situation especially so that he was diagnosed with Mild Depression and was only abusive if he was drunk.”*

In relation to financial problems, gender-based violence is not only recorded among low-income people, although many women in poverty and living in unfavorable backgrounds have less alternatives to escape from violence. On the other hand, because of violence, many women lose their previous economic stability, and get into poverty or social exclusion (Malgesini, G., Sforza, L., & Babovic, M., 2018, July 31). In other words, women may not speak out about abuse if they are afraid their abuser will lose his job, get demoted, or suffer negative reactions from co-workers, especially if she is financially dependent on her partner. (Johnson H., & Fraser J., 2011) Furthermore, Robinson A., & Cook D. (2006) found out in their study that those working to support victims felt that fewer women are likely to retract if they are properly supported.

Further, Table 6 shows the result of the t-test: Two sample Assuming Unequal Variance statistics showing, P(T <= t) two tail (0.562332) gives us the probability that a value of the t-Statistic (-0.58465) would be observed that is larger in absolute value than t Critical two-tail (2.026192). Since the p-value is larger than the Alpha (0.05), therefore the null

hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the means of each sample cannot be rejected. (See Table 6).

Table 6. t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

These findings are consistent with the study of Santos, 2009 as cited by Garcia T, 2020 stating that women stay in abusive relationships for a combination of reasons: for the sake of their children, because culture and society insist the woman is responsible for keeping the family together and that a broken family is not ideal, and or because the woman is economically dependent on her husband and will have no means to support herself and children. In addition, many victims are reluctant in reporting cases of abuse because of the possible consequence of reporting or seeking help because of various reasons which can be related to the effects of Coercive Controlling Violence as cited by Ali, P., Dhingra, K., & McGarry, J. (2015), defined as pattern of emotionally abusive intimidation, coercion, and control combined with physical violence that affects the decision making of the victim.

The role of the community also affects the prevalence of domestic violence abuse cases. In reality, people went through a lot of reasoning to justify whether domestic violence was necessary or not. Although there is a tendency not to blame the victim, the attitude to tolerate the domestic violence in the community must still be considered to be straightened up (Irwan, G. C., & SAEMargaretha, M., 2020).

From the results of the study, it is evident that victims of domestic violence is challenged by various reasons before finally disengaging in the criminal justice process. It is also important to consider that the prosecution of cases and probable conviction of perpetrator is dependent on how the victim will interact and cooperate with the different levels of the CJS. This implicates that the reasons of victim disengagement is needed to be addressed in order to increase and maximize the utilization of related laws with regards to the protection of women and their children's right.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the proportion of violence against women cases in the City of Baguio from case reported to case dismissal shows that victims disengaged in the case filing which affects the investigation and prosecution of the case thus resulting to unsuccessful conviction of perpetrators. The reason of victim disengagement boils down to the high valuation of family in the Philippine culture why women stays in abusive relationship which shows that there is unawareness and misconceptions despite the different laws that aims to protect women and their children. The victims initially seek help from their family members which results to over reliance on mediation process. Lastly victim feels they have received justice if they are already liberated from the relationship and thus pursuing cases is not necessary which is rooted in misunderstanding or non appreciation of the process of CJS.

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